

THE INFLUENCE OF THE USE OF LANGUAGE OF INSTRUCTION ON THE TEACHING AND LEARNING OF MATHEMATICS IN GRADE 4: A CASE OF DWALBOOM CIRCUIT, SOUTH AFRICA

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Abstract

The purpose of this study is to explore the use of language of learning and teaching on mathematics in grade four. The perpetual poor learner performance in mathematics is a compelling factor in this study. The researcher as the long serving grade 4 mathematics teacher chose grade 4 learners because the transition from grade 3 has impacted negatively in the acquisition of mathematics proficiency. They have just graduated from foundation phase where the language of teaching and learning was the mother tongue. In general, the grade 4 performance in maths showed a significant decline compared to their performance in the foundation phase. Hence there was need to investigate the impact of language of teaching and learning. Research questions that guide this study aim are to investigate grade 4 learner's language implications in mathematics, to explore mathematics language that cause poor learner performance, investigate grade 4 experiences in transition from learning mathematics in Setswana to English and explore the challenges grade 4 teachers are experiencing. The study followed a qualitative research approach with case study research design. Population in this study consisted of grade 4 learners and three grade 4 mathematics teachers. Random sampling was used to select ten learners from each school and three mathematics teachers. Data was collected through classroom observation, test, document analysis and interview with mathematics teachers. The researcher used a multiplicity of data collection to interrogate the mathematics language proficiency of grade 4 learners. The researcher believe that mathematics is a language on its own therefore using various data collection methods would answer the research questions. During information collection the researcher discovered that learners who use English from grade 1 to 3 at their schools, have upper hand over learners who used home language from grade 1 to 3. Preliminary findings revealed that learners struggle to understand mathematics concepts when English is used as language of instruction. Furthermore, learners who used English as their medium of instruction in foundation phase seemed to had an upper hand over learners who used mother tongue as their language of teaching and learning in foundation phase.

Keywords: Second language, Language of instruction, Mother tongue.

1. INTRODUCTION

The question of language of instruction is a complex phenomenon across the world. Decisions on language of instruction and efforts to develop materials and instructional strategies to support the selected language(s) are well underway. The language of instruction in this context is English. In South Africa we have 11 official languages but Grade 4 learners could receive education in two languages which are English and Afrikaans. Majority of African learners pursue their education in English as the national language. Most of the

researchers of language of instruction around the world prefer learners to be taught in their mother tongue/home language instruction at least in the early years of education.

Ball (2014) stated that learners, whose primary language is not the language of instruction in schools, are more likely to dropout or fail in earlier grades. Research has shown that children's first language is the optimal language for literacy and learning throughout primary school (UNESCO, 2008:231). The UNESCO publication cited by Ball (2014:127) gives case studies of the strengths and challenges of mother tongue education in Mali, Papua New Guinea, and Peru.

Zafeirakou (2015:54) in underpinning this case, states that "Teaching the foundational skills (early literature and numeracy) and critical thinking in a language that the child speaks and understands is one of the most effective ways to reduce school failure and dropout in the early Grades. More importantly these foundational skills significantly enhance learning later as learners transfer these skills to learning in another language. Goldenberg (2008:235) stipulates that, if feasible, children should be taught reading in their primary language.

2. METHOD

2.1 Research Paradigm

Creswell (2015:321) describes paradigms as the beliefs and actions that guide a field of study. Sefotho (2014:161) argues that paradigms have come to be regarded as similar to the nature of research by way of their core ontological and epistemological presumptions emerging from a distinct world view. As a result, paradigms are central to the craft of research studies (Sefotho, 2014:161).

This study has adopted an interpretive approach as it recognizes that individual experiences and understandings may differ outright, even though all are valid and relevant (Creswell & Poth, 2017). Steyn (2017:132) asserts that the interpretivist paradigm allows a good understanding of social processes and facilitates understanding of how and why these occur. Steyn (2017) further states that it allows for complexity and contextual factors and accommodates changes, should they occur.

2.2 Research Approach

The interpretivist paradigm helps the researcher to describe and understand rather than explain and predict human behavior. This approach recognizes that individual experiences and understandings may differ outright, even though all are valid and relevant (Creswell & Poth, 2017). Steyn (2017:132) states that the interpretive paradigm allows a good understanding of social processes and facilitates understanding of how and why these occur. She further contends that it allows for complexity and contextual factors and accommodates changes if they occur. For this reason, the researcher found the qualitative approach to be appropriate for use in this study.

2.3 Data Collection Instrument

In this study, the researcher has employed a qualitative research approach within an interpretivist paradigm, as it was deemed imperative for this study. This means that qualitative research hinges on the participant's views of the situation being studied (Mertens, 2014:153). A qualitative design encompasses procedures of inquiry such as phenomenology, narratives, ethnographies, and case studies (Creswell, 2013:214).

The choice of a single case study was influenced by the need to have a profound insight on the impact of the use of LoLT on mathematics: A case study of Grade 4 learners, Dwaalboom Circuit, "Limpopo Province." The benefits of a single-case study include the fact that single-case studies are rich and can fully describe the essence of a phenomenon (Yin, 2014). For this reason, the researcher could query old theoretical relationships and investigate new ones. During the investigation process, the researcher used a variety of advantageous data collection mechanisms (Yin, 2014; Creswell, 2013). These methods aided the researcher in collecting a substantial amount of data over a short period of time (Yin, 2014:245). In this context, the researcher explored the use of LOLT in mathematics by Grade 4 learners. This has also encompassed the challenges and experiences the learners encountered when they used English as the MOI.

2.4 Population and Sampling

The research population in this study refers to a target group of Grade 4 learners from three sampled schools. Sampling is an element of the population considered for actual inclusion in the study or a subset of measurements drawn from a population we are interested in (Seaberg, 2003:245). Sampling refers to the

process of selecting a portion of the population to represent the entire population (Johnson & Christensen, 2008), preferably in such a way that they represent the larger group from which they were selected (Gay, 2008). Creswell (2012) claimed that the first step in the research process is to identify the population and places for study.

In this study, the researcher selected participants to answer the research question: *What is the influence of the language of instruction on the teaching and learning of mathematics in Grade 4?*

The selection of research participants for a specific purpose is known as purposive sampling. Kasenga (2007) contended that the logic and power of purposive sampling rest on selecting information-rich cases for an in-depth study. In this context, the information-rich participants are the Grade 4 learners. This type of sampling was based on the objectives the researcher wanted to discover, understand, and gain insight from a sample that contains rich and in-depth information.

The researcher has adopted simple random sampling to select participants. In simple random sampling, each individual case in the population theoretically has an equal opportunity of being selected for the study (Creswell, 2012; De Vos, 2007; Maree, 2007; Neuman, 2006). Therefore, ten Grade 4 mathematics learners were selected from three schools in the Dwaalboom circuit. The discussion about the selection of participants and schools follows below.

2.5 Sampling Method

The study was conducted in three primary schools in the Northam area of Dwaalboom Circuit in Limpopo. The researcher selected three schools that are in his vicinity, of which one is where he is working. For confidentiality reasons, these schools were named School A, School B, and School C. The learners were randomly selected by writing their names on a separate paper, and the researcher randomly drew papers one by one from the lot to select the ten learners from the lot. The names of girls were put in a separate container from the names of boys to ensure gender parity. The same process applied to all identified schools. Learner names in School A were named a to j; in School B, learners were numbered 1 to 10; and in School C, Roman numerals were used from I to x for confidentiality purposes.

A total of 30 (thirty) participants were selected for the study, all of whom were Grade 4 learners, as they were regarded as information-rich. Out of 30 participants, 15 were girls and 15 were boys, to balance gender.

For transparency and ethical obligations, the researcher chose overt observation for the purpose of transparency and ethical obligations. The researcher observed a mathematics lesson about perimeter where learners were taught in English to detect the key challenges of learners being taught in a second language as a medium of instruction. This observation enabled the researcher to collect the necessary in-depth information for the study. The researcher spent one day at each of the selected schools, carrying out observations. The researcher was observing, watching, listening, and drawing conclusions from math lessons on perimeter for thirty minutes in each school.

Primary schools	Pseudonyms	Grade	Age	Gender	
				Boys	Girls
School A	Learner 1-10	4	10 year-old	5b	5g
School B	Learner a-j	4	10 year-old	5b	5g
School C	Learner i-x	4	10 year-old	5b	5g

Table 4.1: *Biographic information of participants*

2.6 Test as Method of Data Collection

This study used tests for data collection, and the purpose was to check the influence of the language of instruction on the teaching and learning of mathematics in Grade 4 when solving mathematics in tests provided to each school. One test was used in each school to measure the level of language proficiency. The main purpose of the test was to check learners understanding of mathematics using English as

instruction when solving mathematical word problems. The researcher administered the test himself at sampled schools immediately after lesson presentations with the respective mathematics teachers.

2.7 Document Analysis

The researcher has perused learners DBE workbooks and assessment school-based tasks for the first term. Documents are valuable as they provide insight into the words and language used by participants during their interactions. For that reason, they are more effective than other research methods. Furthermore, they are easily accessible and less costly. This type of technique is supportive of the results received from tests, DBE workbooks, lesson observation, and learner workbooks. From these documents, the researcher was able to detect the challenges, experiences, and factors influencing the understanding of mathematical concepts by the Grade 4 learners in perimeter.

2.8 Data Analysis

In this study, the researcher analyzed data by comparing scores from written tests, observation notes, and document analysis.

2.9 Data Trustworthiness

Trustworthiness applies to the basic principles of morals in qualitative research (Babbie & Mouton, 2014:167). Trustworthiness can be achieved by establishing credibility, transferability, dependability, and confirmability (Babbie & Mouton, 2014:253). The researcher ensured the trustworthiness of the qualitative research methodology of this study by planning the implementation of the research design, which was conducted in a logical and systematic manner to ensure the trustworthiness of procedures according to the criteria of credibility, dependability, authenticity, and conformability.

3. FINDINGS

The primary outcomes of this study are discussed below according to the themes that have emerged from information collected.

3.1. Theme 1: Challenges Associated with Language of Instruction and Education

In this study, the researcher found that language proficiency with Grade 4 pupils is the main barrier to mathematics understanding. The researcher discovered that learners cannot interact actively with the teacher during mathematics lesson because they do not understand mathematical terms used in a lesson. Results gathered in this theme, assisted the researcher to have an explicit understanding of how learners struggle to comprehend mathematical concepts when English is used as language of instruction and learning. During data collection, it was evident that if teachers do not code switch, learners would not grasp any mathematical concepts throughout the lesson. This could be detrimental to our society because learners will lose interest in mathematics.

3.2. Theme 2: Language Impact on Mathematics

Theme 2 assisted the researcher to explore more in language impact on mathematics. The researcher discovered that learners are unable to answer mathematics questions because of the language used. This became evident when the teacher explains the questions in learner's home language. This failure to answer mathematics activities is a sign to show that learners did not understand the mathematics concepts which the teacher has taught in class. The language impact is a huge barrier in Grade 4 because most the learners miss the basic fundamentals in mathematics, and this could result in learner drop out and/or learners making a general hypothesis that mathematics are difficult. Language plays a pivotal role in understanding mathematical concepts.

3.3. Medium of Instruction

Theme 3 assisted the researcher to gain more insight on language of instruction and education as medium of instruction. This theme made the researcher to be aware that not only do the second language pupils have to compete with a diversity of jargon with mathematical register and changing meanings between registers, but they also need to deal with concepts that do not exist in their home language vocabulary. LoLT makes teaching difficult to teachers in Grade 4 because learners very often confuse mathematical concepts with spoken English and that makes that compels the teacher to resort on code switch in order to accommodate all learners. The main concern for the researcher is that if teachers do not code switch, what

would happen to the learners in order to understand mathematics. This language phenomenon makes mathematics lessons become teacher centered as learners are passively participate because they lack understanding of mathematical terms when English is used.

4. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The next discussions of key findings are linked to the collected works reviewed and empirical study piloted in this research. The following themes emerged from information gathered are discussed below.

4.1 Challenges Associated with Teaching on Mathematics

Research study revealed that learners at all levels are not as they were likely to tune in to the conversation and examined math phonetic, but too to author around their work in logical etymological. Study review, revealed that learners do not comprehend logical concepts, but too illustrate that they are able to join numerical information to others. Besides, key challenges of the impact on second language learners are their capacity to memorize science in English medium environment is the trouble of working with English arithmetic. Collected works audit moreover found that for learners to be able to achieve competently, they must get it the profoundly mechanical phonetic utilized absolutely in science.

4.1.1 Language impact on Mathematics

Literature review has exposed that the effect of the use of language of teaching and education on arithmetic has been a question that concern many mathematics teachers and researchers. Literature found that English proficiency in language of instruction and learning influenced performance in school subjects including math in particular, has led to a various study. Literature review has further discovered that language spoken at home affected learner's education as most of the families use native language for communication yet the language of instruction at school is English.

4.1.2 Language of learning and teaching

Literature audit has uncovered that the requirement for arithmetic instruction through the medium of English is basic from the early review so that learners can be fruitful in arithmetical competency. Writing advance states that the restricted English capability can have an awful effect on learner's insights, and insufficient etymological attainment may impact in actualization of insights. Learners who are instructed in a different language do not accomplish instructive brilliance, since they are less able, but since phonetic obstructions in the arithmetic of etymological speakers. Writing survey has to encourage found that the essential challenges in multilingual classrooms in South Africa is the reality that whereas the control for English is unavoidable, many learners don't have the level of familiarity that empowers them to lock in scientific assignments set in English.

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